

**Guiding Interview Questions (simplified) for our study
“On the Relevance of Industry Participation in Scientific Software Engineering Conferences”**

R. Rabiser, Johannes Kepler University Linz, Austria
K. Schmid, University of Hildesheim, Germany
M. Becker, Fraunhofer IESE, Germany
G. Botterweck, Lero, University of Limerick, Ireland
M. Galster, University of Canterbury, New Zealand
I. Groher, Johannes Kepler University Linz, Austria
D. Weyns, KU Leuven, Belgium and Linnaeus University, Sweden

(1) Joint Understanding:

- What does Software Product Line (SPL)/What does Software Product Line Engineering (SPLE) mean for you?
- What do you consider key activities / properties of an SPL approach?
- What are technological considerations particularly relevant for SPLs?

(2) Experience:

- Describe the organisations in which you worked and the projects.
- What were key experiences related to SPLs?
- What did work well?
- What not so much?

(3) How often have you been at SPLC / involved with SPLs?

(4) Do you think – and if yes, why do you think – fewer (industry) people are coming to SPLC? What is SPLC missing (now)? What would make SPLC more attractive (again)?

(5) What is your view on SPL research (and SE research) back in the day vs. today? What changed?

(6) What is your view on the use of SPLs in industry?

(7) Are SPLC papers relevant for industry? Have you ever talked about/recommended an SPLC paper to someone in industry? Can you share with us, which one was it or what kind of paper it was?

(8) What was the most memorable experience you ever had at SPLC?

(9) What do you think were the most important achievements and what were the most important overlooked aspects in SPL research and practice?

(10) Where do you think SPL research and practice is now (recent developments?) Where do you see SPLE today? Both for you/your company as well as for the industry as a whole?

(11) Where should/will SPL research and practice go?

- What should happen?
- Is there a field which you say sets a good example for the future of SPLs?
- What do you think could be inhibiting factors for the success (or adoption) of SPLs?

(12) Last thoughts/comments?